

Alternate Dispute Resolution Process (ADR): A Need of Present Society

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Abstract

The proliferation of laws and increase in population has resulted in manifold increase in the volume of litigation. The overloaded judicial system is finding it difficult to cope up with the demands on it, having regard to the inherent limitations of the system. The uncertainty about the final outcome, the frequent changes in laws, the enormous expenditure of time, energy and money, associated with court litigations, are taking a toll on the litigant. As a result, people with grievances and complaints have started looking for quicker relief outside law. So the ADR has been introduced.

ADR, is increasingly being adopted as a tool to help settle disputes alongside the court system itself. ADR includes so many formal or informal methods to resolve disputes.

Keywords: ADR, Litigation, Judicial System, Formal-Informal Methods.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian legal system is, technically, a replica of British Pattern. And, this limited system is clumsy and inept to put forward equal access with just result. We need Adequate Justice Dispensing system to uphold tranquility in society and in case any dispute happens to dig up swift and efficient justice. The ADR or Alternative Dispute Resolution is an attempt to devise machinery which should be capable of providing an alternative to the conventional methods of resolving disputes. An Alternative means the privilege of choosing one of two things or course at one's choice.

GENESIS OF ADR

Throughout the World ADR, is promoted as an escape route from the exasperating processes of adjudication. The current phase of the ADR movement began in the U.S. during early 70's. ADR is perceived both as a preventive measure and as a method for channelizing disputes outside the formal 'Judicial' system. The vary reasons for origin of the ADR are the tiresome process of litigation, costs, and inadequacy of the court system. It broke through the resistance of the vested interest because of its ability to provide cheap and quick relief. Such specially devised machinery can also be as describe as "appropriate Dispute Resolution" or "Amicable Dispute Resolution" upon its non-adversial objective.

MEANING AND FUNCTIONING OF ADR

ADR is a process where disputes are settled with the assistance of a neutral third person generally of parties own choice. In its wider sense ADR include Arbitration also because arbitration constitutes an alternative to litigation. In its narrow sense ADR – could cover negotiation, mediation, conciliation etc. The Functioning of ADR in India is mainly two fold (1) Arbitration (2) Settlement through Lok Adalats. Both are institutionalized and work within the bounds of legislation. The mediation and conciliation efforts, be it in labour front, negotiation and conciliation within family courts and tribunals specially appointed for the purpose, operate either directly under a legal framework, or in the shadow of law.

PRESENT LEGAL SYSTEM AND ADR

The attempts to find answers for the problems existing in the present day legal system could be categorized into two (1) revivalist – attempting to traditionalize the system (2) approach of fusion – wherein creative synthesis of Indian and western methodologies are sought. The Institute for the Study and Development of legal system

suggests a three-tier reform action plan. It is an integration of court administration, case management and consensual dispute resolution (CDR). The implementation of these suggestions would be through the ministry of Law and Justice, Government of India, which is expected to insert a series of amendments, especially in procedural laws. The proposed picture seems to be very optimistic but needs the right direction.

The most compelling reasons to adopt an alternative means are (1) access to justice and (2) social harmony. A fine synchronization of litigation that will respond to the rights of the people along with local level alternative methods of dispute resolution wherein one can be responsible to one self and to the society will be a model of aspire.

Types of Alternative Disputes Resolution Mechanism

1. **Arbitration** – Arbitration is the process of solving an argument between people by helping them to agree to an acceptable solution. Arbitration means resolving disputes between the parties as early as possible without getting into procedural technicalities which are associated with the functioning of a civil court. In **Collins v. Collins**, 1882 the court gave a wide definition to the concept of arbitration. It said, ‘An arbitration is a reference to the decisions of one or more persons either with or without an empire, a particular matter in difference between the parties.

Section 2(1)(a) of Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996, defines “Arbitration” as meaning any arbitration matter whether or administered by a permanent arbitral institution.

In State of **J&K v. Dev Dutt Pandit**, AIR 1999 SC 3196 the SC observed that arbitration is an important ADR process, which is to be developed and encouraged.

KINDS OF ARBITRATION

- **Ad-hoc Arbitration** – When a dispute or difference arises between the parties in the course of commercial transaction and course of commercial transaction and the same could not be resolved either through negotiation or mediation, in such cases ad-hoc arbitration may be sought by the conflicting parties. It is not administered by an institution and therefore the parties are required to identify all aspects of arbitration. Ad-hoc proceedings can be faster, cheaper and flexible than an administered proceeding.
- **Institutional Arbitration** – When there is a prior agreement between the parties that in case of any differences or conflicts in the future the matter would be resolved through arbitration and it would be referred to the named institution of which one or more of them are members it is known as institutional arbitration.
- **Contractual Arbitration** – Due to the growth of commercial activities in the modern times there are frequent differences and disputes between the parties which are required to be settled amicably. Thus, to seek early settlement of differences and disputes without taking recourse to the court of law, the parties involved choose to incorporate an arbitration clause as a part of the agreement to refer their future or existing differences to a named arbitrator to be appointed by a designated authority. This is known as contractual arbitration.
- **Statutory Arbitration** – When a law specifies that if a dispute arises in a particular case it has to be referred to arbitration, the arbitration proceedings are called “statutory arbitration”.
- **Fast-track Arbitration** – Fast track arbitration is a time bound arbitration, with stricter rules of procedure, which do not allow any laxity for extension of time, and the resultant delays, and the reduced span of time makes it more cost effective.
- **Mediation** – Mediation is a process in which an external person who is known as mediator works with the transacting parties to resolve the dispute and differences between them. Mediation is always carried out with an assistance of third party. The mediator has no power to impose his/her decision on the parties. The Village Panchayats and the Nyaya Panchayats are good examples of this.
- **Conciliation** – Conciliation is an alternative out-of-court dispute resolution instrument. Conciliation is a voluntary, flexible, confidential, and interest-based process. The parties seek to reach an amicable dispute settlement with the assistance of the conciliator, who acts as a neutral third party. The main difference between conciliation and mediation proceedings is that, at some point during the conciliation, the conciliator will be asked by the parties to provide them with a non-binding settlement proposal. A mediator, by contrast, will in most cases and as a matter of principle, refrains from making such a proposal. Conciliation is a voluntary proceeding, where the parties involved are free to agree and attempt to resolve

their dispute by conciliation. The process is flexible, allowing parties to define the time, structure and content of the conciliation proceedings. These proceedings are rarely public. They are interest-based, as the conciliator will when proposing a settlement, not only take into account the parties' legal positions, but also their; commercial, financial and / or personal interests. Like in mediation proceedings, the ultimate decision to agree on the settlement remains with the parties.

- **Lok Adalat** – The establishment of Lok Adalats under the Legal Services Authority Act, 1987 is one of the alternative means of dispute resolution or redressal.

The word “Lok Adalat” means “People Court”. The Lok Adalat is an old form of adjudicating system prevalent in India which is based on Gandhian Principles. Lok Adalat is another alternative to judicial justice. It is a strategy of delivering of delivering informal, cheap and expeditious justice to the common man by way of settling disputes which are pending in courts and those also which have not reached the courts.

Honorable Delhi High Court has given a landmark decision highlighting the significance of Lok Adalat movement in the case of **Abdul Hasan and National Legal Services Authority v. Delhi Vidyut Board and Others** 1999 IAD Delhi 105. The court passed the order giving directions for setting up of permanent Lok Adalat.

- **Negotiation** – Dictionary meaning of the word Negotiation is discussion aimed at reaching an agreement. Basically, negotiation is a method to settle disputes peacefully by being flexible in various aspects. This method can be applied in every kind of dispute such as technical, legal or political.

EVALUATION OF ADR

I. Merits of ADR – ADR is a socially valuable process for adjusting relations between parties who are in controversy, even if the controversy concerns legal rights and duties. The advantages of ADR are several, such as –

- a) Efficacy
- b) Superior solution
- c) Flexibility
- d) Result oriented
- e) Lessening work load of courts
- f) Specialist Neutrals
- g) Hybrid process

II. Demerits of ADR – Never the less, no system can be faultless and has its own drawbacks. It has its own drawbacks, it has its own obstacles and problems. No phenomenon is problem free. Disadvantages of ADR are not many but they call for attention.

- a) Not magical pill for every case
- b) Prerequisite of consent
- c) Unfamiliarity
- d) Disproportionate Negotiating power
- e) Greater co-operation needed

ADR MECHANISMS IN INDIAN JUDICIARY

ADR was at one point of time considered to be a voluntary act on the part of the parties which has obtained statutory recognition in terms of CPC Amendment Act 1999, Arbitration and Conciliation Act 1996, Legal Services Authorities Act 1987 and Legal Services Authorities (amended) Act 2002. The parliament apart from litigants and the general public as also the statutory authorities like Legal Services Authority have now thrown the ball into the court of the judiciary. What therefore, now is required would be implementation of the Parliamentary object. The access to justice is a human right and fair trial is also a human right. In some countries trial within a reasonable time is a part of the human right legislation, But in our country it is a Constitutional obligation in terms of Article 14 and 21. Even before the existence of section 89 of CPC, There were various provisions that gave the power to the courts to refer disputes to mediation, which sadly have not really been utilized. Such provisions, interalia, are in Industrial Disputes Act, The Hindu Marriage Act and the Family Court Act and also present in a very nascent state from via section 80, Order 32 A and Rule 5 B of Order

27 of the CPC. A trend of this line of thought can also be seen in *ONGC vs. Western Co. of Northern America*. AIR 674, 1987 SCR (1) 1024 and *ONGC vs. Saw Pipes Ltd.* AIR 2003 SC 2629. Industrial Disputes Act 1947 provides the provision both for conciliation and arbitration for the purpose of settlement of disputes. Section 23(2) of the Hindu Marriage Act 1955, incorporates that for the purpose of reconciliation, the court may adjourn the proceeding for a reasonable period and refer the matter to person nominated by court or parties with the direction to report to the court as to the result of the reconciliation.

IMPORTANCE OF ADR OR ADR – WHY NEEDED

1. **Amicable settlement of disputes** – ADR provides for a friendly settlement of disputes. In business it is a prudent approach to have a competitor not a rival. It is clear that a healthy competition brings improvement and it's also cost effects cost of service or commodities in every sphere.

- **Speedy disposal of trial** – ADR provides for speedy disposal of trials. Unlike litigation process in ADR there is no scope of adjournment or stay order.
- **Economical settlement of disputes** – Unlike litigation process where huge expenses are incurred to pay the advocates and other people involved in the trial, in ADR it is not the case and minimum amount of money is required.
- **Time saving management** – In ADR the dispute is resolved without following the cumbersome procedure of ordinary litigation that's why ADR is also known as dispute management.
- **Legal recognition** – This system has been recognized in the Indian Statutes. For instance – now the Civil Procedure Code, 1908, Order 32-A, Rule 3 contains scope for compromise and the decree evolved from that compromise is not appealable. Notably, section 12 of the Industrial Disputes Act, 1947 contemplated provisions for conciliation as pre-requisite for any pressure tactics / collective bargaining.
- **Advent of multinational corporations** – A number of multinational corporations are coming to invest and establish their business. These businesses have dynamic approach in their business activities. Therefore, in case of disputes they should be provided with such a mechanism which can resolve their dispute immediately and without delays.

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MECHANISMS

- Courts are authorized to convey directives for the adoption of ADR mechanisms by the parties and for that purpose Court must play important role by way of giving guidance. Power is additionally conferred upon the courts so it can intervene in numerous stages of proceedings. But these goals can't be achieved unless requisite infrastructure is provided and institutional frame work is put to position.
- Awareness can be brought by holding seminars, webinars and workshops. ADR achievement programs have to be organized so that the mindset of lawyers, parties in conflict and judges can be changed.
- Training of ADR practitioners should be held by the universities, colleges and institutes. Training of ADR should be made a part of university curriculum.
- Judicial officers must be trained to identify the cases which can be solved outside the courts.
- ADR mechanisms should be made more viable because inflow of cases cannot be stopped as the doors of judiciary are not closed but the outflow can be increased by providing other means of dispute resolution.
- Mediation centers can be setup in districts and tehsil areas which will help the citizens to resolve their disputes quickly and without going for litigation process which is a time taking process.
- Not everyone can afford litigation as it is an expensive process so ADR methods should be taken to panchayat and nyaya-panchayat levels (rural areas).
- The conclusion arrived at the ADR should be made binding upon the parties which is not the case at present and the parties are allowed to appeal in the court if allowed to appeal in the court if they wish.

CONCLUSION

It is a well-known fact that there are plenty of cases pending in Indian courts due to lack of resources including human resources and infrastructure. According to the National Judicial Data Grid, there are about 73 lakh cases pending across the country. Although, various steps have been taken towards the improvement of the system such as speeding up the judicial process, the establishment of new courts and increasing the number of judges,

etc. Besides this, in 1999 the union government has amended Section 89 of Civil procedure Code 1908 and mandated the courts to try out the possibilities of resolving the pending disputes through arbitration or mediation or Lok Adalat which is known as ADR system. Although the aforementioned steps have been taken the problem still continues.

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